

Tuesday Oct 29. 72

Dear Andrew,

Have sent off passport details and photos.
Thanks for your photos.

A telephone call from my baby in Boston this morning about a letter from Muscat. She is sending me the details of the letter by post and I will write further later.

Generally, initial reaction very favourable. Application was handed in and well received though everything is shut down for Ramadan. Oil company was favourable as well, although the overall boss of oil company had brought in Karen F. he doesn't want a Danish monopoly so was pleased the another application. Karen F. wants to dig graves in Wadi Tiji and Ibbi - both on natural route from Buraimi to coast. So I don't think we'll overlap. She has applied to do sandalwood I gather, so we ought to be ready to do same.

Finally I gather it is pretty certain we won't be gone in shape to arrive Oman before January 1st at earliest. The negotiator will take that long. So you can ease off worrying about early starts.

Will write again after I get the letter & papers. Meanwhile keep touching wood for continued progress.

Best from the Princess.